

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PATHOLOGIES CAUSED BY FUNGI IN AZERBAIJAN AND THEIR RESEARCH

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Abstract

The fact that the nature of the Republic of Azerbaijan is also under the influence of the changing ecological conditions of the increasingly globalized world, and the qualitative changes in the country's economy as a result of Azerbaijan's restoration of independence in 1992, necessitated a review of the measures taken in connection with these phytopathological studies. Thus, as a result of changes such as the country's transition to a market economy, the transfer of land to private ownership, and the replacement of collective farms and state farms by private farms, the place of a number of state organizations that were supposed to control the phytosanitary condition of the country was not determined in time in the newly formed economic system, the collapse of the communication mechanism intended to ensure their material and technical base, and the impossibility of creating a new one in a short time, put those organizations in a state of actual inactivity. All this significantly increased the likelihood of the spread of diseases and the emergence of new diseases. Among them, diseases caused by fungi are of particular importance both due to their distribution area and danger. Because fungi differ from other microorganisms (bacteria) that are carriers of pathology, as well as from organized particles (viruses) in terms of their biological activity and the number of pathologies they cause.

Keywords: ecological conditions, vegetation, biotope, fungi

Before proceeding to the analysis of mycological studies conducted in Azerbaijan, which has a rich vegetation cover and forests occupy up to 11% of its territory, it would be appropriate to dwell on one issue. In general, pathologies caused by fungi were studied and the results obtained in the context of mycological studies conducted until the middle of the last century were given together [3,4,8]. However, over time, in accordance with the level of development of science, studies began to be grouped according to their nature, so that similar cases did not bypass Azerbaijan, and studies in this direction began starting from the middle of the second half of the last century [1,4,5,7,12]. Although many of the studies conducted at first were episodic in nature, serious studies were also included towards the end of the last century. This can be clearly seen from the information provided below.

From the results of the research conducted in this field, it can be said that in Azerbaijan, the causative agents of diseases such as rust, downy mildew, powdery mildew, trachymycosis, anthracosis, Dutch disease, cancer, necrosis, wilting (verticellosis), leaf curling, etc. are considered relatively widespread, and the biotopes in which they are spread include both natural (forests) and artificial (agrophytocenoses, biosphere reserves, parks, etc.) biotopes. In studies conducted with trees common in artificial and natural forests, it was determined that *Cylindrocarpon willkommii* (Lindau) Wolenw. (teleomorph- *Nectria ditissima* Tul.), *Microsphaera alphitoides* Griff. & Maubi., *Gloeosporium quercinum* West. *Nummularia bouillardi* Tul. are carriers of the most dangerous pathology for the main tree species - trachymycosis, and the morphological signs of a number of their species (*Ceratocystis roboris*, *C. ulmi*, *C. castanese*) vary depending on the nutrient environment.

Studies conducted on the study of pathologies observed in fruit trees growing in the territory of Azerbaijan can be considered more extensive both in number and scope [12-14,16]. From studies conducted in this direction, it was found that the number of diseases associated with fruit plants is more than 50. Among these diseases, the most dangerous are alternariosis in figs (caused by *Alternaria ficis* Farn.), powdery mildew (*Oidium erysiphoides* Fr.), phyllosticosis, and leaf curling in stone fruits (*Taphrina deformans* (Berk.) Tul.), powdery mildew (*Sphaerotheca pannosa* (Wall.) Sacc.) and others (root rot, fruit rot). Fungal species such as *Cylindrocarpon radiclecola* Wr., *Fusarium oxysporum* Schlecht., *Gliocladium verticilloides* P. D. Pl. are more actively involved in the development of root rot. Although the causative agents of these diseases belong to different taxonomic groups, their representatives belonging to biotrophs in terms of trophic relationships are more numerous [6].

The mycobiota of dry subtropical plants such as figs, almonds, pistachios, sycamores and innab have been studied for their taxonomic structure, frequency of occurrence, pathologies caused by them and their degree of spread, as well as phytotoxic activity. It was determined that the mycobiota of subtropical fruit plants such as figs, figs, almonds, pistachios and peanuts includes 89 species, which, according to their taxonomic affiliation, belong to 52 genera, 5 classes, 15 orders and 21 families of 4 subphyla (Zygomycota, Ascomycota, Basidiomycota and Deuteromycota) of the true fungi department (Euomycota) of the kingdom of fungi (Mycota). 3 of the fungal species included in the mycobiota of the studied dry subtropical fruit plants (*Aspergillus versicolor* (Vuill.) Tiraboschi, *Ascochyta fagi* Woronich and *Coniofora puteana* (Fr.) Karst) were

recorded for the first time for the mycobiota specific to the nature of Azerbaijan.

There are certain research works on the study of cultivated plants in Azerbaijan, and from these studies it is clear that a certain part of the above-mentioned dangerous pathogens has also spread in Azerbaijan and causes a decrease in the productivity of this or that plant [3-7,12,15,16]. For example, as a result of the conducted research, the mycobiota of fungi spread in Absheron was comprehensively studied in terms of its taxonomic structure, frequency of occurrence on host plants, activity of hydrolytic enzymes and phytotoxic properties, and it was determined that the mycobiota of cultivated plants studied in Absheron includes 86 species of fungi and fungus-like organisms, 81 of which belong to the Mycota and 5 to the Chromista kingdoms. The recorded fungi cause various diseases (spotting, fusarium, wilting, rot, rust, powdery mildew, phytophthora, etc.) in plants cultivated in Absheron, and the prevalence of these diseases is between 1.35-43.2%. Vegetable and melon plants cultivated in different zones of Azerbaijan were also analyzed for the species composition of their mycobiota, as well as for the transmission of pathologies through seeds, a number of fungal species prevalent in these plants were described, and the distribution of new species for the Azerbaijani mycobiota was also revealed. In addition, diseases caused by fungi in some agricultural plants cultivated in Azerbaijan were identified and the dynamics of the spread of some of them were studied.

In the studies conducted in the Mughan Plain, plants specific to the area, including cultivated ones, were purposefully studied for the species composition of their mycobiota, areal classification, and diseases caused by phytopathogens involved in the formation of mycobiota [1,3,7,9,12]. It has become clear that 172 species of fungi participate in the formation of the overall mycobiota of the Mugan Plain, and among them, species such as *Aspergillus ustus*(Bain)Thom et Church, *A. sulphureus*(Fres)Thom et Church, *Aschophyta cytisi* Lib., *A. gladioli* Trav., *A. iridis* Oud., *Fuzarium culmorum*(W.G.Sm.) Sacc., *Puccinia iridis*(DC.)Wallr. and *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk. were recorded for the first time in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The fact that the fungi recorded in this area cause about 40 pathologies was also one of the results obtained in the studies conducted in the Mugan Plain.

Research conducted in the area called "Sultanbud Forest" of Aran Karabakh revealed that 137 species of true fungi participate in the formation of the mycobiota of cultivated and growing plants there, of which 8 (*Podosphaera clandestine*(Fr.)Leveille, *Sphaerotheca fuliginea* Poll., *Uromyces trifolii-repentis*(Cast.)Liro *Meruliopsis taxicola* Fr., *Alternaria mali* Roberts, *Colletotrichum trifolii* Bain et Essary, *Ascochyta* [4-8,11,14,16] . *trifolii* Bond. et Truss and *Diplodina lycopersici* Hollos) were recorded for the first time in research conducted in Azerbaijan. In addition, it became clear that the pathogenic representatives of fungi recorded in the studied areas were determined to cause about 95 pathologies and a 3-point system was proposed to assess their degree of danger.

As is known, many species of fungi cause various diseases in both cultivated and wild plants, as a result of which the biological productivity of plants decreases, and the products they produce undergo qualitative and quantitative changes, and in most cases this change is unambiguously characterized as negative in terms of practical demand. One of such diseases, and one of the most dangerous in recent times, is fusarium wilt, and this disease is found all over the world [2,5,8,14]. Fungi of the genus *Fusarium* are involved in the development of this disease. The dangerous aspect of the disease caused by these fungi is that it is most often found in cereal plants, which are the main food source for humans and a number of living beings. On the other hand, as a result of this disease, not only the biological productivity of plants decreases, but at the same time, the product obtained from such diseased plants is also enriched with metabolites formed as a result of the vital activity of fungi of this genus. Such metabolites include mycotoxins (for example, deoxynivalenol-DON, diacetoxyrirpenol-DAS and zearalenone-F-2, fumanin B-1, etc.), the fact that they are also dangerous to human health is one of the accepted realities of today [5,8-12,16]. Research materials on the study of this fungus are found in studies conducted in Azerbaijan. For example, studies conducted in the Mughan Plain determined that these fungi cause fusariosis in the studied areas and that 6 species of the *Fusarium* genus were involved in the occurrence of this disease. In general, it became clear that 9 species of fungi belonging to the *Fusarium* genus are widespread in Azerbaijan and almost all of them participate in the occurrence of fusariosis in one combination or another [1-3,7,11,14]. Therefore, one of the results of the studies conducted was that determining the permissible limit of the amount of fungi belonging to the *Fusarium* genus, both themselves and the mycotoxins they produce, in cereal plants is important for ensuring the microbiological safety of products obtained from cereal plants. By the way, it would be appropriate to mention one issue related to the genus *Fusarium* [14,16]. Thus, there are several taxonomic systems characterizing fungi belonging to the genus *Fusarium*, which have been the focus of special attention in recent times, the authors of which are V.B. Bilay, Nicholson P. et al. and Xi K. et al. Despite such differences, it is accepted that this genus has a wide species diversity. It should only be noted that there are 55 species of internal diversity and 22 forms of the genus *Fusarium*.

During the analysis of the results of some studies, it became clear that the phytopathogenic activity of fungi in cereal plants is associated with the various diseases they cause, and the most common fungal diseases were identified as root rot, fusarium, septarium, white rot, rust, powdery mildew, various types of spotting, wilting, etc. It has become clear that the mycological state of a number of agrophytocoenoses currently used for the cultivation of agricultural plants in Azerbaijan is not yet very dangerous, but the increasing spread of a number of diseases and the lack of advanced regulatory documents that allow for a

comprehensive assessment of the danger of fungi can make the situation inevitable to change at any time.

In addition, other studies have also provided information on the mycobiota of plants cultivated in Azerbaijan, for example, the characterization of cereal plants such as wheat, barley and corn as places where microorganisms themselves and their metabolites accumulate in both "steppe" and warehouse conditions, the presence of medicinal and essential oil plants cultivated in Azerbaijan among the substrates where fungi settle, the dominance of northern, i.e. boreal elements in the formation of mycobiota specific to Azerbaijan, etc. can be an example of this.

However, the results of the studies conducted so far do not allow for a generalization, even superficially, of issues related to crop losses caused by the diseases caused by these fungi, the patterns of spread of pathogens, their distribution in different ecological zones of Azerbaijan, etc. Conclusion: As noted, the Kur-Araz lowland is a place that occupies the largest plain area of Azerbaijan and occupies the largest area in the agricultural sector, especially in terms of irrigated lands. Until our studies, this area, with the exception of the Mughan plain, has not become the subject of systematic studies conducted in the mycological aspect. If we add to the above that the spread of fungal diseases, as well as the quantitative indicator of the virulence of a pathogen considered to be a particular disease, are also related to environmental factors, then the necessity of conducting studies in the Kur-Araz lowland based on the principle of "a specific approach in specific conditions" is beyond doubt.

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